

Dynamic Model of Dividend Payout Companies in Indonesia

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Abstract: This study attempts to test the dynamic dividend payout model on non-financial companies in Indonesia. Dynamic models have advantages compared to static models. The Dynamic models take into time account, while static models do not take into this account. The calculation of the time in the dynamic model is done by entering the lag variable. The dynamic model in this study includes dividend payout lag variables and eight other factors, they are profitability, firm size, investment ratio, asset structure, leverage, operating risk, corporate tax rates, and interest rates as the independent variables. Samples that collected were 192 non-financial companies listed in the Indonesia Stock Exchange in the 2011-2016 periods. The results of this study indicate that the variable lags in dividend payout, profitability, firm size, investment ratio, asset structure, corporate tax rate, and interest rate which have a positive effect on dividend payout, while leverage has a negative effect on dividend payout, while operating risk does not affect dividend payout. This study also shows that non-financial companies in Indonesia implement a stable dividend payout with a speed of adjustment to targeted dividends of 59,97% and a long-term target payout ratio of 69,54%. The speed of adjustment to targeted dividend low indicates that dividends do not increase in large numbers but gradually increase by considering the long-term targeted dividend payout ratio. Stability dividend will make the company have good performance in the capital market.

Keywords: Dynamic Model, Targeted Dividend, Speed of Adjustment.

I. Introduction

Dividend payout still becomes the most debatable topic in the financial literature. Dividend payout is important because it is a recurring decision made by the company which will affect the company's capital structure decisions. In addition, dividend payout concerns on the interests of many parties so that the proportion of dividend payments needs careful consideration the management.

Dividend payout in research conducted by Lintner (1956) applied a dominant pattern of dividend payout because it focused more on previous dividends and company profitability in making dividend payout decisions. This encourages researchers to explore other factors that might influence dividend payout in making decision. Therefore, the topic of determinants of dividend payout and stability of dividends is increasingly becoming a concern of researchers in various countries in which the application of a stable dividend payout will make the company has a better value in the capital market. Dewenter and Warther (1998) found a speed of adjustment to targeted dividends. The results of his research showed that all companies in the United States had an adjustment speed of 5,5% while companies in Japan had an adjustment speed of 9,4%. The classification of companies in Japan also shows the speed of adjustment, namely the keiretsu company by 11,7%, hybrid companies by 8,2%, and independent companies by 2,1%. This shows that Japanese keiretsu member companies are adjusting dividends faster than hybrid companies, US companies and independent Japanese companies.

Furthermore, several studies use the Lintner method (1956) to find the speed of adjustment and the target payout ratio of dividend to assess the stability of dividends. The application of a stable dividend payout was found in the United States with an adjustment speed ratio of 30% and a target dividend payout ratio of 50% (Lintner, 1956), Jordan with an adjustment speed ratio of 42,9% and a target dividend payout ratio of 47,8% (Al-Najjar, 2009), and Vietnam with an adjustment speed ratio of 12,3% and a target dividend payout ratio of 88,6% (Tran and Nguyen, 2014). On the other hand the adoption of an unstable dividend payout was found in Turkey with an adjustment speed of 100% and a target dividend payout ratio of 51,7% (Adaoglu, 2000), Tunisia with an adjustment speed ratio of 96,59% and a target dividend

payout ratio of 12% (Ben Naceur, et al., 2006), Pakistan with an adjustment speed of 41,90%-77,33% and a target dividend payout ratio of 18% -55% (Ahmed and Javid, 2008), India with an adjustment speed ratio in the pre-reform period of 34% and in the post-reform period 63% and a target dividend payout ratio in the pre-reform period was 16% and in the post-reform period of 11% (Kamat and Kamat, 2009, 2013).

In accordance with the presentation of various studies above, it has been shown that the use of the Lintner model to test the stability of dividends has been widely carried out. Based on the results of research in various countries, it shows that many companies make adjustments to targeted dividends and have a long-term target payment ratio. Therefore, the researchers want to test the determinants and stability of dividends in cases that are applied to companies in Indonesia.

II. Theoretical Framework and Hypotheses

The Shareholders' compensation for their investments can be in the form of dividends or capital gains. There are two types of dividends namely cash dividends and stock dividends (Hanafi, 2015). Dividend payout will be determined in the general meeting of shareholders. The Formulation of dividend payout requires careful consideration from the management because it involves the interests of many parties.

The Dynamic models have more advantages than static models. The Dynamic models take time aspects into account, while static models do not take into account time (Widarjono, 2017). The calculation of time in a dynamic model is done by entering the lag variable. The variable impact of the lags allows the company not to be at the targeted / optimal dividend level. The dynamic model in this study includes the variable lag of dividend payout (DPR_{it-1}) and eight other factors as the independent variables. The relationship between variables and the development of hypotheses in this study can be explained as follows:

2.1. The Effect of Lag in Dividend Payout on Dividend Payout

Lintner (1956) conducted a research by developing a statistical model to consider the smoothing process in dividend payments. The significance variable of the lags dividend payout is the first indication of the stability of dividends, because the management must consider the trend of previous year's dividend payments to follow a stable dividend payout (Adaoglu, 2000). Furthermore, the positive value indicates that the company makes a speed of adjustment (SOA / δ) ratio of dividend payments at the targeted / optimal level because the optimal value (1 or 100%) minus the lag variable variable coefficient positive dividend payout yields an adjustment $0 < \delta < 100\%$ (Widarjono, 2017). Thus, the variable lag of dividend payout is expected to have a positive influence on this year's dividend payout.

H1: Variable lags in dividend payout have a positive and significant effect on dividend payout.

2.2. Effect of Profitability on Dividend Payout

Al-Najjar (2009) and Jabbouri (2016) stated that profitability is an important factor in determining dividend payout. The Companies with high profitability will be more capable to pay dividends. Kamat and Kamat (2009, 2013), Kamat (2016); Labhane and Mahakud (2016) agreed on these opinions with the results of their research stating that large companies would gain greater profitability and distribute higher dividends. Ben Naceur, et al (2006) added that with an optimal investment payout, it would encourage the acquisition of high profitability, so as to produce greater free cash flow and ultimately pay high dividends. Kuwari (2009) found that the legal protection of shareholders in the Gulf Cooperation Council Stock Exchange (i.e. Kuwait, Saudi Arabia, Oman, Qatar and Bahrain) is low, just like in other developing countries. Therefore, when profitability increases, it will encourage the shareholders to have high dividend payments as well. Al-Najjar and Kilincarslan (2017) found that the higher the profitability of the company, the higher the company will pay dividends as a signal of better financial performance. This condition is supported by signaling theory. When profitability increases, the company will deliver good financial performance by paying high dividends, while when profitability decreases, the company will convey a decrease in financial performance by paying low dividends. Thus profitability has a positive influence on dividend payout.

H2: Profitability has a positive and significant effect on dividend payout.

2.3. The Effect of Firm Size on Dividend Payout

Large companies have easier access to the capital market compared to small companies (Al-Najjar and Kilincarslan, 2017; Jabbouri, 2016). The ease of access to the capital market is due to the maturity of large companies (Al-Najjar, 2009) and higher institutional share ownership (Labhane and Mahakud, 2016). The ease of access to the capital market is very

meaningful for flexibility and ability to obtain external funds, so that large companies can allocate their internal funds to pay higher dividends to shareholders. Large companies will face high agency costs due to dispersion of ownership, increased complexity, and inability of shareholders to closely monitor company activities. Therefore, large companies pay high dividends to reduce agency costs (Kuwari, 2009). Large companies are also more diversified so that the risk of failure is lower than for smaller companies. Company size is inversely proportional to probability of bankruptcy (Kamat and Kamat, 2009, 2013 and Kamat, 2016). In addition, large companies are overseen by the analysts, so they are expected to pay high dividends to provide good information about company prospects (Kamat and Kamat, 2009, 2013 and Kamat, 2016). Thus, the size of the company has a positive influence on dividend payout.

H3: Firm size has a positive and significant effect on dividend payout.

2.4. The Effect of Investment Ratio on Dividend Payout

Asadi and Oladi (2015) showed that companies in Tehran when faced a high investment ratios are also able to increase the ratio of dividend payments. The companies that made investment can produce profit, so they can distributed the dividend to the stockholder. Thus, the investment ratio has a positive influence on dividend payout. The hypothesis proposed is:

H4: Investment ratio has a positive and significant effect on dividend payout.

2.5. Effect of Assets Structure on Dividend Payout

Kamat and Kamat (2009, 2013) stated that companies with many tangible assets will have a deeper ability to owe, so that the internal funds can be allocated to pay high dividends. Whereas companies with little tangible assets will have a low ability to owe, so that they will follow a residual payout where their internal funds are prioritized to finance the company's operations and pay low dividends. Thus, the asset structure has a positive influence on dividend payout. The hypothesis proposed is:

H5: Asset structure has a positive and significant effect on dividend payout.

2.6. The Effect of Leverage on Dividend Payout

Companies that have low debt levels will have the ability to pay high dividends, while companies with high debt levels will pay low dividends to reduce their dependence on external funding (Al-Najjar, 2009; Jabbouri, 2016). Ben Naceur, et al (2006) added that debt can play a role in disciplining high dividend payments. High dividend payments can be considered as wealth transfers from debt holders to shareholders. Therefore, increasing debt will encourage companies to pay low dividends. In line with Al-Najjar and Kilincarslan (2017), it is stated that debt plays a role in substituting dividends in controlling agency problems in which the companies in Turkey that have a lot of debt tend not to pay dividends. Besides that, the pecking order theory states that the company will choose financing from internal funds compared to the use of debt. If the internal funds are low, the company will adjust to pay a low dividend compared to debt in order to distribute high dividends. Companies with a low debt ratio will also have a low risk of bankruptcy, so that the company is able to pay high dividends. Whereas if there is an increase in debt ratio, it will increase the burden of repayment and increase the risk of bankruptcy, thereby reducing the ability to pay dividends (Labhane and Mahakud, 2016; Gohar and Alam, 2018). Debt agreements also prohibit higher dividend payments (Kamat and Kamat, 2013). Therefore, a high debt ratio will encourage companies to pay low dividends. Thus, leverage has a negative influence on dividend payout.

H6: Leverage has a negative and significant effect on dividend payout.

2.7. The Effect of Operating Risk on Dividend Payout

Based on the pecking order theory, companies with high operational risk will have a high income volume and will accumulate cash when earnings are good. The accumulated income will be used to invest in the future rather than paying dividends. Therefore, companies with high operational risk will have high income volumes and low dividends (Kamat and Kamat, 2009, 2013). Al-Najjar (2009) added that the higher the risk of a company, the higher the possibility of the companies' bankruptcy. These conditions have an impact on the smaller opportunities for companies to pay dividends.

H7: Operating risk has a negative and significant effect on dividend payout.

2.8. The Effect of Corporate Tax Rate on Dividend Payout

Samuel and Inyada (2010) found that there is positive effect of corporate tax on dividend payout. The company will pay low dividends to minimize shareholders' personal taxes. This condition is supported by the theory of tax preference, where taxes on capital gains are lower than taxes on dividends, while the company will pay high dividends if the tax on capital gains is higher than the tax on dividends. Besides that, an increase in corporate tax triggers an increase in dividend payments can also be caused by not dominating corporate taxes in influencing company profits. This condition allows companies to pay high dividends from retained earnings. The sample companies in this study tend to be matur. Thus it is necessary to encouraging shareholders to continue to get high dividends despite an increase in corporate tax. This condition is supported by the client effect theory, where the shareholders of companies in Indonesia selected as the samples in this study prefer high dividend payments as a return on the investment they have made.

H8: Corporate tax rate has a positive and significant effect on dividend payout.

2.9. The Effect of Interest Rate on Dividend Payout

The interest rate can have a positive or negative effect on dividend payout. Ofori-Sasu, et al. (2017) found a positive effect of interest rates on dividend payout. The increase in interest rates will require shareholders to get a higher dividend payment as a return on their investment in order to compensate or reduce the effect of increasing the interest rate. In addition, an increase in interest rates triggered an increase in dividend payments can also be caused by a reduction in the company's dependence on external funding through debt and shifting to new share issuance (equity), so that companies provide returns through high dividend payments to shareholders.

H9: Interest rates have a positive and significant effect on dividend payout.

III. Hypotheses Development and Empirical Research Model

3.1. Sampling Techniques

The object in this study was the Non-Financial Industries listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) in the period 2011 to 2016. Data is taken from Indonesian Capital Market Directory 2011-2016. The sampling technique used was purposive sampling method. There were two sampling criteria used. First, the companies distributed dividends within the period of observation (2011-2016). Second, companies had data over a period of six years (2011-2016). Based on the two criteria, it is resulted in a total sample of 192 companies.

3.2. Operational Definition and Variable Measurement

The dependent variable in this study was dividend payout. Dividend payout was proxied by the Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR) ratio, which was a dividend per share of earnings per share.

There were nine independent variables in this study, namely as follows: **1) Lag in Dividend Payout or Previous Year Dividend (DPR_{t-1}).** **2) Profitability (PRFT).** Profitability is abbreviated as PRFT and is proxied using the Return on Asset (ROA) ratio. Through Return On Assets (ROA), we can measure a company's ability to generate net income based on total assets. **3) Firm Size (SIZE).** The size of the company is abbreviated as SIZE and is proxied by the natural logarithm of total assets. **4) Investment Ratio (INVR).** The investment ratio is abbreviated as INVR and is proxied by the PBV ratio, which is the stock market price per share against the book value of share capital per share. **5) Tangibility of Assets (TNGA).** The asset structure is abbreviated as TNGA and is proxied with net fixed assets against total assets. **6) Leverage (LEV).** Leverage is abbreviated as LEV and is proxied by the proportion of debt usage to total assets. **7) Operating Risk (ORSK).** Operational risk is abbreviated as ORSK and is proxied by the standard deviation ratio of operating income to total assets. **8) Corporate Tax Rate (CTAX).** The corporate tax rate is abbreviated as CTAX and is proxied by the total tax payment to the total pre-tax profit. **9) Interest Rate (INRT).** The interest rate is abbreviated as INRT and is proxied by the lending interest rate growth.

3.3. Data Analysis Technique

The impact of any economic payout or business activity does not occur instantly but requires time (Widarjono, 2017). The time interval is called lag. The formation of a dynamic model takes time into account by entering the lag variable. The dynamic regression model that was used in this study is a partial adjustment model (PAM) which was included the dependent lags variable as an independent variable.

The measurements using static models assumed that all coefficients of the lags variable did not differ from zero, in other words it limited the previous period so that it did not have any impact on the current year. The Static models were

used to estimate dividend payments targeted by the company. The dividend payment ratio targeted by the company in this study can be formulated as follows:

$$DPR_{it}^* = \beta_0 + \beta_1 PRFT_{it} + \beta_2 SIZE_{it} + \beta_3 INVR_{it} + \beta_4 TNGA_{it} + \beta_5 LEV_{it} + \beta_6 ORSK_{it} + \beta_7 CTAX_{it} + \beta_8 INRT_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

In ideal conditions, the ratio of observed dividend payments should be the same as the ratio of dividend payments targeted by the company. In these conditions, it can be concluded that the dividend changes observed from the previous period should be the same as the changes needed to reach dividends targeted by the company at a certain time. The formulation can be written as follows:

$$(DPR_{it} - DPR_{it-1}) = (DPR_{it}^* - DPR_{it-1}) \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Kamat and Kamat (2009, 2013) stated that the company always tried to reach the ratio of dividend payments targeted, but the adjustment costs and flotation costs caused the company not succeed in achieving the targeted dividends. Therefore, the company tried to adjust the ratio of the dividend payments observed to be close to the ratio of dividend payments targeted by the company. This leads to the use of a partial adjustment model (PAM). Thus, the partial adjustment model (PAM) in this study can be formulated as follows:

$$(DPR_{it} - DPR_{it-1}) = \delta (DPR_{it}^* - DPR_{it-1}) \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

or

$$DPR_{it} = \delta \beta_0 + a_0 DPR_{it-1} + \sum_{k=1}^k a_k X_{kit} + v_{it} \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

Where; $a_0 = (1 - \delta)$, $a_k = \delta \beta_k$, and $v_{it} = \delta \varepsilon_{it}$.

Thus, the research regression model in full can be formulated as follows:

$$DPR_{it} = \delta \beta_0 + (1 - \delta) DPR_{it-1} + \delta \beta_1 PRFT_{it} + \delta \beta_2 SIZE_{it} + \delta \beta_3 INVR_{it} + \delta \beta_4 TNGA_{it} + \delta \beta_5 LEV_{it} + \delta \beta_6 ORSK_{it} + \delta \beta_7 CTAX_{it} + \delta \beta_8 INRT_{it} + v_{it} \dots \dots \dots (5)$$

Where DPR^* is the ratio of dividend payments targeted by the company, X is the independent variable, k is the number of independent variables, DPR is the ratio of observed dividend payments, $PRFT$ is profitability, $SIZE$ is firm size, $INVR$ is investment ratio, LEV is leverage, $ORSK$ is operating risk, $CTAX$ is the corporate tax rate, $INTR$ is the interest rate, δ is the speed of adjustment, $(1-\delta)$ is the speed of adjustment towards the targeted dividend of the company, ε and v are error term, subscript i is $1 \dots N$ representing company, subscript t is $1 \dots T$ representing time.

Model testing was carried out using the ordinary least square / OLS (common effect) model, which was pooled EGLS (Estimated Generalized Least Square) cross section weights. According to Gujarati (2012), "General Least Square (GLS) is a procedure of transforming the model and the applying OLS to them. In sort, GLS is OLS that satisfies the standard least square assumptions. The estimators thus obtained are known as GLS estimators, and it is these estimators that are BLUE (Best Linear Unbias Estimator)". Thus, the pooled EGLS test has transformed the variables to meet the least square standard, thus the estimator obtained is called the GLS estimator and in a BLUE form.

IV. Result and Discussion

4.1. Statistic Descriptive

Descriptive statistical test aims to describe the condition of the data used in the study. The results of the descriptive analysis of each variable in this study are as follows:

Viewed from 192 research samples, The average ratio of dividend payments distributed to shareholders from net income obtained by 192 samples was 45,693%. The average log size of the company at the industry is 12, 86966. The average value of the current stock price was 5,905417 times higher the book value. The average proportion of net fixed assets to total assets from 192 samples was 27, 7065%. The average proportion of debt usage to total assets was 44,681%. The average standard deviation ratio of operating income was 4, 2094. The average corporate tax rate of total pre-tax profit was 24, 0536%. The average lending interest rate growth was -3, 0167%.

4.2. The Determinant of Dividend Payout

The results of the partial adjustment model (PAM) regression test using panel data are shown in table 1 is as follow:

Table 1.
Test Result

Variable	Regression Coefficient	Standard Error	t-statistic	Sig.
Konstanta	-0,788074	0,180117	-4,375341	0,0000
DPR _{t-1}	0,400273	0,061794	6,477544	0,0000
PRFT	0,417031	0,220356	1,892528	0,0603
SIZE	0,078062	0,012489	6,250502	0,0000
INVR	0,006145	0,003170	1,938734	0,0544
TNGA	0,117010	0,063787	1,834384	0,0686
LEV	-0,289735	0,067132	-4,315928	0,0000
ORSK	-0,135390	0,357215	-0,379014	0,7052
CTAX	0,172745	0,086376	1,999916	0,0473
INRT	0,127428	0,035198	3,620343	0,0004
F-statistic : 55,32449with Sig = 0,0000				
R ² : 0,768490				
Adj. R ² : 0,754599				
N : 192				
Dependent Variable: Dividend Payout (DPR)				

Source: Data Analysis Results

Based on the results of the regression, the Partial Adjustment Model (PAM) equation can be obtained as follows:

$$DPR = -0,788074 + 0,400273DPR_{t-1} + 0,417031PRFT + 0,078062SIZE + 0,006145INVR + 0,117010TNGA - 0,289735LEV - 0,135390ORSK + 0,172745CTAX + 0,127428INRT + e$$

The above equation shows the results of the t test, namely the influence of individual independent variables on the dependent variable as follows: The results of testing the first hypothesis (H_1) indicate that the lag in dividend payout / the previous year dividend payout (DPR_{t-1}) has a positive effect (t-statistic = 6,477544) and significant (significance t = 0,0000 <0.01) towards dividend payout (DPR). Lag variable (previous lag) dividend / dividend payout in the previous year (DPR_{t-1}) has a regression coefficient of 0,400273 and it is positive. This means that every 1% increase in the proportion of lags in dividend payout / the previous year's dividend (DPR_{t-1}) will increase the dividend payout (DPR) by 40,03% assuming that the other variables are constant. Furthermore, the speed of adjustment coefficient can be known from the optimal value (1 or 100%) minus the dividend payout lag variable coefficient (DPR_{t-1}) or δ . Based on these equations, the speed of adjustment (SOA / δ) coefficient on dividend policies targeted at non-financial companies in Indonesia is (1- δ = 1-0,400273) or 0,599727. This value shows that the difference between the realization of dividend payout and dividend payout targeted by the company is adjusted by 59,97% in a year. It also can be said that to reach the targeted dividend need 1,66 year.

Based on the Partial Adjustment Model (PAM) equation, coefficients in the short term and coefficients can be obtained in the long run. The coefficients obtained from PAM regression are coefficients in the short term, while the long-term coefficients are obtained from short-term coefficients divided by the adjustment coefficients (Widarjono, 2017 and Basuki, 2017). The target payout ratio (TPR) is the long-term coefficient of the PRFT variable, which shows the reactive dividend payout on profitability. The value of the target payout ratio (TPR) in this study is 0,695368 or 69,54%. Thus, determining the dividend payout of non-financial companies in Indonesia also considers the long-term payment ratio seen from its profitability (TPR of 69,54%). These results indicate that companies in Indonesia implement smoothed residual dividend policies because they estimate the target ratio of long-term dividend payments (Hanafi, 2015).

The profitability had a positive effect (t-statistic=1,892528) and significant (significance t=0,0603 <0,10) on dividend payout (DPR). Profitability has a regression coefficient of 0,417031 and it is positive. This means that every 1% increase in the profitability, will increase the dividend payout (DPR) of 41,70% by assuming other variables are constant.

The firm size has a positive effect (t-statistic=6,250502) and significant (significance t=0,0000 <0,01) on dividend payout. Firm size has a regression coefficient of 0,078062 and it is positive. This means that for every increase of 1 unit of firm size, the dividend payout (DPR) will increase of 0,078062 by assuming other variables are constant.

The investment ratio has a positive effect (t -statistic=1,938734) and significant (significance $t=0,0544 < 0,10$) on dividend payout. The investment ratio has a regression coefficient of 0,006145 and it is positive. This means that for every 1% increase in the investment ratio, the dividend payout will increase of 0,61% by assuming other variables are constant.

The asset structure has a positive effect (t -statistic=1,834384) and significant (significance $t=0,068668 < 0,10$) on dividend payout (DPR). Asset structure (TNGA) has a regression coefficient of 0,117010 and it is positive. This means that for every 1% increase in asset structure (TNGA), it will increase dividend payout (DPR) of 11,70% by assuming other variables are constant.

The results of the sixth hypothesis testing (H_6) show that leverage has a negative effect (t -statistic = -4,315928) and significant (significance $t = 0.0000 < 0,01$) on dividend payout. Leverage (LEV) has a regression coefficient of 0,289735 and it is negative. This means that every decrease of 1% leverage (LEV), it will reduce dividend payout (DPR) of 28,97% by assuming other variables are constant.

The operating risk has no significant effect (significance $t = 0,7052 > 0,10$) on dividend payout (DPR) but the direction is negative (t -statistic = -0,379014) according with the hypothesis proposed. Operating risk has a regression coefficient of 0.135390 and it is negative. This means that for every 1% decrease in operational risk, it will reduce dividend payout of 13.54% by assuming other variables are constant.

The corporate tax rate has a positive effect (t -statistic = 1,999916) and significant (significance $t = 0,0473 < 0,05$) on dividend payout. The corporate tax rate has a regression coefficient of 0,172745 and it is positive. This means that for every 1% increase in the corporate tax rate, the dividend payout (DPR) will increase of 17,27% by assuming other variables are constant.

The interest rate has a positive effect (t -statistic = 3,620343) and significant (significance $t = 0,0004 < 0,01$) on dividend payout. The interest rate has a regression coefficient of 0,127428 and it is positive. This means that for every 1% increase in the interest rate, the dividend payout will increase of 12,74% by assuming the other variables are constant.

Based on the results of the F test showed that nine independent variables in this study jointly have a significant effect (significance $F=0,000000 < 0.01$) on dividend payout (DPR). Furthermore, based on the results of the accuracy test (R^2 test), the adjusted R^2 value is 0,754599 which indicates that 75,46% of dividend payout (DPR) can be explained by the nine independent variables in this study, while the remaining 24,54% is explained by variables others outside the model.

4.3. Discussion

The results of the analysis show that the lag of the dividend payout or the previous year's dividend (DPR_{t-1}) has a positive and significant effect on dividend payout. The positive direction shows that the higher the dividend the previous year, the higher the dividend payout and vice versa. These results are in accordance with the first hypothesis proposed and supported by Lintner (1956), Dewenter and Warther (1998), Ben Naceur, et al (2006), Ahmed and Javid (2008), Al-Najjar (2009), Kamat and Kamat (2009, 2013), Tran and Nguyen (2014), Al-Najjar and Kilincarslan (2017), Gohar and Alam (2018), and Zagonel, et al (2018) research. The company adjusts the dividend payout ratio at the targeted / optimal level because the optimal value (1 or 100%) minus the lag dividend variable coefficient value of positive so that dividend payout will produce an adjustment value of $0 < \delta < 100\%$ (Widarjono, 2017). Based on these results, it can be concluded that non-financial companies in Indonesia have speed of adjustment (SOA/ δ) to reach the targeted dividend payout is 59.97%. Non-financial companies in Indonesia make adjustments to dividend smoothing at a moderate level such as the findings of Al-Najjar and Killincarslan (2017). Furthermore, it indicates that non-financial companies in Indonesia apply a stable dividend payout. This means that dividends do not increase in large numbers but gradually increase by considering the targets. Similar results are also found by Lintner (1956), Al-Najjar (2009), and Tran and Nguyen (2014).

The results of the analysis show that profitability has a positive and significant effect on dividend payout. Positive direction shows that the higher the profitability, the higher dividend payout and vice versa. These results are in accordance with the second hypothesis proposed and supported by Ben Naceur, et al (2006), Al-Najjar (2009), Kamat and Kamat (2009, 2013), Asadi and Oladi (2015), Jabbouri (2016), Kamat (2016), Labhane and Mahakud (2016), and Al - Najjar and Kilincarslan (2017) research.

The results of the analysis show that firm size has a positive and significant effect on dividend payout. Positive direction shows that the larger the size of the company, the higher the dividend payout and vice versa. These results are in accordance with the third hypothesis proposed and supported by Al-Najjar (2009), Kamat and Kamat (2009, 2013), Asadi and Oladi (2015), Jabbouri (2016), Kamat (2016), Labhane and Mahakud (2016), and Al-Najjar and Kilincarslan (2017) researches.

The results of the analysis show that the investment ratio has a positive and significant effect on dividend payout. Positive direction shows that the higher the company's investment ratio, the higher the dividend payout and vice versa. These results are in accordance with the fourth hypothesis proposed and supported by Asadi and Oladi (2015) research.

The results of the analysis show that the asset structure has a positive and significant effect on dividend payout. Positive direction shows that the more tangible assets the higher the dividend payout and vice versa. These results are in accordance with the fifth hypothesis proposed and supported by Kamat and Kamat (2009, 2013) researches.

The results of the analysis show that leverage has a negative and significant effect on dividend payout. Negative direction indicates that the higher the leverage, the lower the dividend payout and vice versa. These results are in accordance with the sixth hypothesis proposed and supported by Al-Najjar (2009), Kuwari (2009), Kamat and Kamat (2009, 2013), Asadi and Oladi (2015), Jabbouri (2016), Kamat (2016), Labhane and Mahakud (2016), Al-Najjar and Kilincarslan (2017), and Gohar and Alam (2018) research.

The results of the analysis show that operational risk does not significantly influence dividend payout, but the negative direction is in line with the seventh hypothesis proposed. The fluctuations in income earned by the company will trigger higher uncertainty of profits to be shared with shareholders. Therefore in this study, it was considered inaccurate when applied to companies that have a constant growth in profit. Thus the high and low business risks faced by the company will not affect the payment of dividends to shareholders. The same results were also obtained by several studies. Kuwari (2009) found that non-financial companies listed on the Gulf Cooperation Council Stock Exchange (ie Kuwait, Saudi Arabia, Oman, Qatar and Bahrain) in determining their dividend payout take into account agency and company conflicts rather than business risks. Andriani and Amanah (2017) also found that risk does not affect dividend payout.

The results of the analysis indicate that the corporate tax rate has a positive and significant effect on dividend payout. Positive direction shows that the higher the corporate tax rate, the higher the dividend payout and vice versa. These results are in accordance with the eighth hypothesis proposed and supported by Samuel and Inyada (2010) research.

The results of the analysis show that the interest rate has a positive and significant effect on dividend payout. Positive direction shows that the higher the interest rate, the higher the dividend payout and vice versa. These results are in accordance with the ninth hypothesis proposed and supported by Ofori-Sasu et al. (2017) research.

V. Conclusion

The Samples that collected were 192 non-financial companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in the 2011-2016 period. The results of this study indicate that the variable lags in dividend payout, profitability, firm size, investment ratio, asset structure, corporate tax rate, and interest rate have a positive effect on dividend payout, while leverage has a negative effect on dividend payout. While operating risk does not affect dividend payout. This study also shows that non-financial companies in Indonesia implement a stable dividend payout with a speed of adjustment to targeted dividends of 59,97%. The speed of adjustment to dividends targeted low and high long-term payment targets indicates that dividends do not increase in large numbers but gradually. Based on the F test, it is known that nine independent variables in this study jointly have a significant effect on dividend payout. The adjusted R² value is 0,754599, indicates that 75,46% dividend payout can be explained by the nine independent variables, while the remaining 24,54% is explained by other variables outside the model.

There are several suggestions submitted by the author for various parties. The company should consider the variable dividend lag and the long-term target payout ratio based on its profitability in determining dividend payout. If the SOA value is less than 100%, then the company applies dividend smoothing and the company applies a stable dividend payout. Companies that implement a stable dividend payout will get a better valuation in the capital market, so that they are expected to attract more investors to invest their capital. Investors should pay attention to the dividend lag payout, profitability, firm size, investment ratio, asset structure, leverage, corporate tax rate, and interest rate because all eight factors have a significant influence on the determination of dividend payout. Information on the eight factors can later be used as a consideration before investing in a company. On other hand further research is expected to extend the observation period, adding other independent variables that have not been studied in this study.

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